

TECHNOLOGY LEVEL - FINDINGS MATRIX

Market Practices	Composite Activities	Designable Elements	Underlying Single Activities	Consequences	Illustrative Quotes from In-depth Interviews (Sayings)	Excerpts from Unobtrusive Observation and Document Analysis (Doings)
Representational Practices	Comprehending the blockchain configuration (PEDERSEN et al., 2019)	Core technology infrastructure technologies	Understanding the trade-offs for each type of blockchain	Allows to frame the technology in a useful way	<p>"Are we going to upload a network? No, we will use a network that has already gone up, a vacant infrastructure, so for me, our decision for the Ethereum at the first moment to prove the concept seems obvious." (P1)</p> <p>"More people started doing things in Fabric, and also, for large corporations doing in Fabric is kind of more obvious because you have, 'oh it is not open source', so, there is the model that has been created, like this, it is open source; but there is big tech here to support you." (P1)</p> <p>"So I came to this conclusion: indeed, blockchain without crypto, like an incentive mechanism, it does not make sense, because when the network is small, and you control everything via contract, as the business starts to grow for thousands of nodes and thousands of participants, you will not be able to enforce the contract on everyone, and it is good that you have a mechanism that aligns the interests." (P13)</p> <p>"Now, the main thing about this project is also to define governance. Not just the governance of the network, navigation, the consensus mechanism, but the governance of what should or should not be applied in this network, precisely avoid this type, of wanting to put something that another solution might be straightforward, cheaper, and more effective." (P5)</p> <p>"Because there is an aspect of the blockchain, that is this thing of immutability is a double-edged sword, which I think people say little about it. We have a frame that we worked on over a governance framework to deal with this story of you being able to make changes. And then when you think about it and talk, man, but then how do I do it? If I can change the trust, it becomes useless; then you need to create a governance for that." (P3)</p> <p>"[...] it is not enough for you to have the technology, you have to develop the ecosystem, you have to define how the tokenization process occurs, what is the tokenization process that is happening, what is the asset that I am tokenizing under what circumstances, how does this first mile take place here, and the edges, the output of that too, how does the conversion of what used to be cryptoasset happen and then I reconnect everything with the real economy." (P6)</p>	<p>Firm A has conducted a public consultation to analyze possible platforms to be used in their solution. According to the result publicly available, different platforms were suggested by the community with different trade-offs. However, in the end, they opted for the Ethereum ecosystem since it offers the possibility of using a public network with many nodes distributed around the world and creating permissioned networks (content extracted from Firm A website).</p> <p>Firm A has been co-leading the development of a public blockchain for the public sector in which the governance occurs through the agreements for construction and operation of the network, with common standards, in public-private partnership. They propose that the network nodes can be divided between different institutions of the government (content extracted from a presentation file explained by P3 in a public innovation event).</p>
					Orchestrating a governance framework	Increases the confidence on the outcomes

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Representational Practices	Portraying a development process (PORRU et al., 2017)	Product technology Process technologies	Co-developing with different stakeholders	Encourages innovation through collaboration	<p>"this blockchain market is still at a time with very low competition and has more collaboration than competition, because it is one of the new markets." (P1)</p> <p>"[...] I used to say, in the token, there is no way for the guy to 'workaround' and every time we presented the idea, we keep improving it because people always found a way to 'workaround'. (P1)</p> <p>"So it is people investing in this technology for future appreciation which are paying the salary of the guy who's working on it now. So we need to make the entry of investments in crypto feasible so that this business attracts more people so that developers can work and develop their projects, right?" (P13)</p>	<p>Firm A and Firm C have made available source code of their respective projects in the Github (a hosting platform for version control and collaboration). This open source initiative enables the community to analyze their code as well as suggest issues to be improved (content extracted from Github projects of Firm A and Firm).</p>
			Building the solution	Denotes different strategies of product/service development	<p>"Everything under development is made in company. Everything is developed by the company, from the application, from the software, applications, APIs, everything is developed at home." (P11)</p> <p>"I consider Firm B to be a bit a 'root' startup in the sense that we did it without money and this was very good. Maybe at first you do not think so, money is always lacking and you have to be creative." (P7)</p> <p>"It is a competitive advantage, but I think we are just the narrator of this story. We are not characters, we are narrators. That is what I said at the beginning. It is a privileged view. But everyone else, everyone can try to be a narrator; it is much more challenging to go there and do a project in crypto than to tell a story, and keep talking about that a project is good or bad." (P16)</p> <p>"I do not know if you have an crypto exchange account. Maybe you will agree with me that the user experience is awful. The user experience sucks in every way, and one of Firm B's flags is being simple, being elegant, is having a sex appeal in use." (P8)</p> <p>"[...] there is the question of usability of the accountability at the border, right. Look, man, you have lost your private key, and you're kind of wrapped up, although, in our solution, you have reasonable alternatives." (P3)</p> <p>"[...] the usability is a very critical point and it is a critical point that you have a security trade-off because if you start to improve usability a lot, sometimes you start to lose security, you have to provide solutions that keep you secure, given that this is a differential of the technology, but improves usability." (P1)</p>	<p>The app of Firm B in the Google Play is considerably well evaluated. They account for hundreds of user evaluations and demonstrates a special attention by answering positive and negative feedbacks. We could notice several compliments regarding the usability and user interface which denotes a attention to the software quality process (content extracted from Google Play page of Firm B).</p>
			Detecting usability as a challenge	Enables to provide to the customer a suitable user experience	<p>"This part of cyber risk was a great learning for us. We always focused a lot on this security issue. We closed a partnership with [omitted], they were even expensive, but it was just to protect us from hackers." (P7)</p> <p>"[...] a pioneer in crypto security, it has at least two very strong components, the first of which is asset storage. We started from the beginning. We were pioneers in the use of institutional custody, using the best practices, we were kind of discovering the best actors in the world to safely custody and store cryptocurrencies." (P14)</p> <p>"I think that the main evolution was the institutional custody solutions, which today [omitted] does, [omitted] itself, who also entered this market. That was this fundamental evolution. We could not offer the service that we offer today if it did not have a safe way to store the cryptoasset for the long term, safe and independent, you know? That we did not want to control private keys." (P13)</p> <p>"[...] possibly, I would have more perspectives, but today, quickly, what comes to mind is the agility. The agility today... even today has courses, agile process methodology, this is spreading a lot. The internet is very fast. So, today, what brought us with this differential that can help us in this delivery and the quality, is agility." (P10)</p> <p>"You have to have the right people by your side. Spend time recruiting. And the interests have to be very aligned. Everyone has to have the same goals. Whatever it is." (P7)</p> <p>"As a founder, a leader in the company, you have to worry all the time, obsessively, with people, with people's success, okay? And it is very easy for you to lose your attention because the business brings others things that seem more urgent or important to you, but are not." (P14)</p>	<p>Firm B has dedicated a supporting webpage to widely explain to its customers a series of functionalities from its app, such as transferring cryptocurrencies or depositing bitcoins in the wallet (content extracted from supporting webpage of Firm B).</p>
			Strengthening the security	Enables to provide to the customer a reliable experience	<p>"if you are not aware, it is a business that pulls the technology, not the technology that pulls the business, so you have to have a solution to a problem, and you have to have the owner of the problem." (P5)</p> <p>"Look, innovation in any company is a virus, the company will react and will want to kill, it will react, it will fight that business [...]. The organism will fight, it will fail, it will discredit fails. "This is useless, just a waste of time", so the technology I see as great... The blockchain technology for Firm A in this line of transparency, besides being a pain, it is pain from the whole company." (P5)</p> <p>"So, we have been supported by the executives. Of course, this depends a lot on building together with the executives, showing value to them as well as the executives understand the value." (P4)</p>	<p>Firm D published a post in their Instagram profile explaining how the transactions are signed in a protected manner and how independent auditors monitor this process (content extracted from Firm D Instagram profile).</p>
			Being agile with the right people	Guarantees a qualified and productive development process	<p>Firm A has coordinated an internal innovation contest from which their own employees realized the solution based on the use of tokens in an illustrative example of intrapreneurship and open innovation (content extracted from Firm A website).</p>	<p>A C-level executive of Firm F has the routine of periodically sharing their progress in their Instagram and blog covering both product and business development. This communication enables the stakeholders to notice a constant evolution and delivery of value (content extracted from Instagram profile and blog of Firm F).</p>
			Coping with the innovation process	Reveals the needs encompassed into the coordination of a innovation process		